

Hospital wastewater as a source of vancomycin in the environment

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Abstract

Vancomycin (VAN), an antibiotic from WHO watch group, for Gram-positive bacterial infections, was detected in all analysed hospital wastewater samples across Poland, with significant seasonal and regional variability. In the hospital sewage samples examined, the concentration range of this drug varied from 1.2 to 49 940.7 ng L⁻¹ in the winter period, and from 0 to 75 216.4 ng L⁻¹ in the summer period. It should be noted, however, that the median (1306.4 ng L⁻¹) was higher for the summer period. Correlation analysis revealed a strong association between VAN levels and total organic carbon and total nitrogen, suggesting seasonal influences on antibiotic presence in wastewater. Additionally, negative correlations between VAN and selected anions indicate potential interactions affecting antibiotic persistence. These findings underscore the need for improved hospital wastewater management to mitigate antimicrobial resistance and environmental contamination.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Anions, hospital outflows, total organic carbon, wastewater, vancomycin

INTRODUCTION

Vancomycin (VAN), a glycopeptide antibiotic with a tricyclic structure, has long been recognized as a critical therapeutic agent in combating infections caused by Gram-positive bacteria, particularly those resistant to other antimicrobial agents. VAN belongs to the WHO “watch” group, comprising antibiotics with a higher resistance potential, including critically important antimicrobials. Due to resistance risks, these antibiotics require strict monitoring in healthcare. Clinically, vancomycin treats respiratory, skin, and endocardial infections, including in paediatric and neonatal patients. Despite its critical role, the emergence of vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE) and *S. aureus* strains poses a growing challenge to healthcare systems worldwide.

Hospital environments serve as significant reservoirs for vancomycin-resistant organisms, with VRE being highly prevalent in intensive care units. Enterococci, a major cause of nosocomial infections, exhibit a remarkable capacity for acquiring and disseminating resistance genes. Hospital wastewater, often containing high concentrations of antimicrobials and resistant bacteria, represents a critical pathway for the environmental dissemination of antimicrobial resistance.

Recent studies have confirmed the presence of VRE and vancomycin residues in hospital effluents, municipal wastewater, and food production systems, underscoring the necessity of stringent wastewater management. As key interfaces between clinical and natural ecosystems, hospital outflows facilitate the spread of resistant pathogens and antibiotic residues, necessitating comprehensive mitigation strategies.

This study investigates hospital wastewater as a potential source of vancomycin contamination in the environment. Effluent samples were collected from hospitals across all regions of Poland during winter and summer to assess seasonal variations in vancomycin concentrations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Samples analysis methods

Wastewater samples were collected from hospitals in provincial capitals in Poland including,

Warsaw, Katowice, Lublin, Kielce, Łódź, Rzeszów, Białystok, Gdańsk, Toruń, Gorzów Wielkopolski and Zielona Góra (both in lubuskie), Szczecin, Wrocław, Poznań, Olsztyn, Opole, and Kraków, during winter and summer seasons. Due to procedures related to the possibility of sharing data on the hospitals themselves and the need to maintain confidentiality, at this point the authors must limit themselves to providing the names of the cities in which the hospitals were located. Samples were centrifuged, filtered, and analysed for VAN occurrence and concentrations using the Ultimate 3000 HPLC system coupled with a QTRAP 4000 mass spectrometer equipped with a triple quadrupole-linear ion trap analyser (AB Sciex LLC, USA). Anions such as fluorides, chlorides or sulphates were quantified using ion chromatography Dionex Aquion (Thermo Scientific, Poland), while total organic carbon and total nitrogen levels were measured with TOC-L analyser (Shimadzu, Japan). Statistical analysis was performed to evaluate correlations between VAN concentrations, anions and TOC ranges.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

VAN concentrations

VAN was detected in all analysed hospital wastewater samples, with notable variability between geographical location of the sampling point and seasons [Figure 1]. Figure 1a. represents the results of summer campaign, showing elevated VAN levels in wastewater collected from hospitals located in highly urbanized cities in Poland, with a population of over 650,000 inhabitants [i.e. Wrocław (49 940.70 ng L⁻¹) and Łódź (24 541.36 ng L⁻¹)], though overall concentrations are significantly lower than in summer period. Figure 1b. depicts summer samples, highlighting similarly elevated values in wastewater collected from both cities [Wrocław (67 025.00 ng L⁻¹) and Łódź (75 216.42 ng L⁻¹)], with a noticeable gradient of lower concentrations across northern and eastern regions, which is often associated with less urbanization of these areas.

Figure 1. Variability of VAN concentrations in hospital wastewater collected from the capital cities of Poland's provinces during two distinct seasons: a) winter and b) summer

Study by Bengtsson-Palme and Larsson (2016) indicate that the predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC) for VAN ranges from 600 to 8 000 ng L⁻¹. Other research suggests that vancomycin concentrations in influent wastewater should range from 900 to 43 700 ng L⁻¹ with levels in treated effluent reaching up to 8 500 ng L⁻¹.

In the present study, vancomycin concentrations exceeded these thresholds during both winter and summer seasons. Notably, in wastewater collected from the area of Wrocław, winter concentrations reached 49 940.7 ng L⁻¹, and summer levels rose further to 67 025 ng L⁻¹. A similar trend was observed in samples collected from the area of Łódź, where concentrations peaked at 75 216.42 ng L⁻¹ in summer hospital effluents. These findings align with previous studies that report higher bacterial infection rates, particularly methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, in spring and early summer, as well as the impact of air conditioning on bacterial transmission. The observed seasonal

variability supports these findings, indicating that vancomycin levels in hospital wastewater may correlate with increased antibiotic use during periods of higher infection prevalence.

TOC and TN correlations

This analysis highlights the importance of understanding the seasonal dynamics and regional variability of VAN pollution in relation to nitrogen and organic carbon levels [Figure 2]. Both TN and TOC concentrations increase during summer compared to winter. This trend reflects the seasonal dynamics of nutrients and organic matter in aquatic environments, likely influenced by higher temperature or increased microbial and other living organisms' activity. VAN concentrations also rise significantly during summer in wastewater collected from hospitals of most cities, particularly around Wrocław and Łódź, suggesting increased usage of VAN in hospitals.

Figure 2. Correlations between TN and VAN, as well as TOC and VAN, across voivodeship cities in Poland during two seasons: winter (a, b) and summer (c, d)

The correlation between both TN and TOC with VAN is stronger in summer compared to winter. These results suggest that VAN concentrations in hospital wastewater are more closely associated with nitrogen and organic carbon levels during warmer months, potentially due to seasonal variations in hospital activities or environmental factors influencing pollutant persistence and transport.

Anions

Analysis revealed significant negative correlations between VAN concentrations and certain anions. Higher fluoride and chloride levels were associated with lower VAN concentrations, suggesting potential interactions. A similar inverse correlation was noted for sulphate ions in both seasons.

Table 1. Pearson correlation coefficient values

Correlations	Winter		
	Cl ⁻ /VAN	F ⁻ /VAN	SO ₄ ²⁻ /VAN
PCC*	-0.088	-0.14	-0.008
Correlations	Summer		
	PCC	-0.3	0.08

A higher concentration of sulphates, fluorides, and chlorides in hospital outflows may indicate a significant environmental concern, as these compounds are commonly associated with various chemicals used in medical treatments, disinfectants, and pharmaceuticals.

CONCLUSIONS

This study confirms the widespread presence of VAN in hospital wastewater across Poland, with significant seasonal and regional variability. Seasonal trends indicate increased VAN concentrations during summer, likely driven by higher antibiotic use associated with peak infection rates and environmental factors affecting pollutant persistence. Strong correlations with TN and TOC suggest nutrient-driven VAN dynamics, while negative correlations with anions indicate potential stability and transport interactions. These findings highlight the need for enhanced hospital wastewater management strategies to mitigate the environmental release of VAN and its potential role in the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance.

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